

THE HAWTHORNE STUDIES AS A GROUND-BREAKING WORK IN THE FIELD OF MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

The Industrial Revolution of the 18th and 19th Centuries led to the emergence of mechanized factory system and new manufacturing processes. The large scale of operations, modern methods, use of lower-cost labour, and the increased production among other factors characterizing the new work forms necessitated the emergence of management as an area of expertise.

The early day management principles were built around pure scientific forms of management as against charismatic leadership. Organization leaders operated with the belief that human beings are like machines, are inherently lazy and solely motivated by money.

The adopted management principles were autocratic in nature and led to managers encountering some difficulties and frustrations until in the 1930's when Elton Mayo's team conducted the Hawthorne experiments. The experiments revealed that when workers believe that they are valued, taken care of and get opportunities to be involved in decision making, they contribute more to increase in productivity levels as against when their physical work environment is improved on.

The Hawthorne studies which revealed that employees like other humans are social animals that always desire to be heard and valued, and this is what motivates them and ultimately enhances their productivity. This human relations side the studies introduced to the field of management laid a foundation for what is called Human Resources management today.

1.0 Origin of Modern Organizations and Management

The Industrial Revolution of the 18th and 19th Centuries led to the emergence of modern work organizations and the factory system. This created new forms of organizations and there was a major shift from family subsistence businesses like farming and fishing to profit-oriented large-scale business operations. This meant new methods of doing many things had to be introduced as previous management methods were no longer applicable. Managers could no longer maintain records in their heads or make on-the-spot decisions.

The switch to the machine operations of factories from the hand-held tools of subsistence family businesses introduced new challenges such as socio-technical problems of machine operators and lack of experience generally in the operations of large scale businesses. Hence, management had to evolve as an area of expertise. Early day management theorists like Frederick Taylor and Henri Fayol proposed foundational management theories that were put to practice.

1.1 Scientific Management and Frederick Taylor

The introduction of large-scale business operations led to specialization of tasks and departmentalization within organizations. One person could no longer perform all tasks but specialized in performing a few tasks. This led to a need to coordinate, integrate and systemize the workflow. In the late 1880s, Frederick Taylor, a young mechanical engineer after observing workers at a steel company figured many workers put in less than their maximum effort, a gesture he tagged soldiering.

Taylor attributed the act of soldiering to the fact that workers had no reason to put in maximum effort since most wage systems of that time were based on attendance and worker position. Taylor suggested a piece-rate system of payment, he believed it would work if workers believed the standards were set fairly and management would stick to the standard. Taylor wanted scientific and empirical methods rather than the traditional setting for work standards to be used. His efforts marked the beginning of scientific management.

The main principles of Taylor's scientific management were:

- ✓ Scientific methods of designing jobs against trial-and-error methods
- ✓ A division of work resulting in higher interdependence
- ✓ A hierarchy of authority and strict control of subordinates
- ✓ High pay for high-performing employees

Scientific management produced new attitudes in superiors and subordinates towards their duties and towards each other. It was a new ideology about the use of human efforts emphasizing operational efficiency through maximum output with minimum effort. Emphasis was placed on specialization and division of labour and the concept of line management surfaced. Wage incentives were developed scientifically to motivate employees and managers began to monitor actual performance once standards were set. Thus began the managerial function of control.

1.2 Henri Fayol's Theory of Management

Henri Fayol, in the early 1900s, was the first to issue a thorough statement on general management. He identified 14 principles of management as follows:

- ✓ Division and specialization of work
- ✓ Formal positional authority
- ✓ Discipline based on obedience and respect
- ✓ Unity of command – employee receives order from only one superior
- ✓ Unity of direction
- ✓ Group interests ahead of individual interests
- ✓ Fair remuneration both to employee and organization
- ✓ Degree of centralization be dependent of formal communication channels and situation
- ✓ Scalar chain – line of authority and formal communication channels
- ✓ Order – a place for everything
- ✓ Equity – managers should be kind and just towards employees equally
- ✓ Stability of tenured personnel
- ✓ Initiative – individual zeal and energy in all efforts
- ✓ Harmony and unity within organization

The works of Fayol and Taylor are complementary, they are tagged classical theorists due to their studies being foundational in the field of management. They both established management of personnel and material resources is central to organizational success and both applied a scientific approach. The main difference is that Taylor's orientation was towards management of work while Fayol's was towards the management of the organization. Fayol and Taylor's works however attracted various reactions, commendations, and criticisms.

1.3 Reactions to the Classical School of Management theories

Karl Marx (1818 – 1883) criticized the new ways of working and tagged it as exploitative towards workers. He saw the concept of specialization and division of labour as a means to put workers under firm control and domination. He opined fragmentation of jobs was to prevent workers from having complete mastering of the job so as not to be able to hold the employer to ransom. In essence, no particular worker would have dominance or control over his own job.

Marx saw it as making humans appear as a small part of a machine. Hence his natural creativity is removed and he is subjected to being a tool or machinery the organization uses, up to the point it affects his relationship with his colleagues, resulting in alienation.

Émile Durkheim (1858-1917), another classicist saw specialization and division of labour in a different way from Karl Marx. He claimed it existed in the traditional setting as the simple moral/ethical acts through which workers and family members showed solidarity through support, even though they could all survive on their own. He called that of the traditional setting the 'mechanical' form of division of labour.

Durkheim's tagged the modern organization's division of labour and specialization 'organic'. Organic in the sense that an organism needs all its parts (organs) united even though they perform different functions. So he rather saw it uniting.

Asides from the reactions of Marx and Durkheim, the early day management theories faced several criticisms. Most of the disapprovals were centered on the principles being systemic rather than charismatic. That workers were treated like inanimate machines without feelings, the belief

humans are solely motivated by money, autocratic management, strict control over subordinates, one-way communications with no considerations for human behavior or social factors were all contributing factors to the criticisms.

These factors led to managers encountering difficulties and frustrations because people did not follow their predicted patterns of behaviour. It was found that the classical management principles did not achieve complete production efficiency and workplace harmony.

2.0 The Hawthorne Experiments

The shortcomings of the classical management approach with respect to achieving production efficiency and workplace harmony led to an increased interest in helping managers deal more with the 'people side of organizations.

Elton Mayo, an Australia-born sociologist, and Fritz Roethlisberger led a group of researchers in the 1930s to conduct an experiment at the Hawthorne plant of Western Electric Company, which made the telephone hardware for AT&T. The study revealed that employee productivity is not the function of only physical conditions of work and monetary compensation.

The experiment comprised of four parts:

1. Illumination Experiment
2. Relay Assembly Test Room Experiment
3. Interviewing Programme
4. Bank Wiring Test Room Experiment

- 1. Illumination Experiment:** This experiment was carried out to find out the relationship between output and illumination. When the intensity of light was increased, the output also increased. The output continued to increase even when the illumination was gradually reduced to the normal level. This led to the conclusion that there is no

dependable relationship between the output of workers and the illumination of the work environment. It has to be some other factors that affect productivity.

2. **Relay Assembly Test Room Experiment:** The aim of this part was beyond finding out the impact of illumination on production but also to establish the effect of other physical such as working hours and rest hours. In this experiment, a small homogeneous work-group of six girls was asked to work in a very unofficial atmosphere and observed. Productivity and morale increased appreciably during the period. However, the productivity kept rising and stabilized at a high level even when all the improvements were taken away and pre-test conditions reintroduced. The researchers deduced that socio-psychological factors such as the feeling of being important, recognition, attention, participation, cohesive work-group, and non-directive supervision held the key for higher productivity.
3. **Mass Interview Programme:** The aim of this program was to make a systematic study of workers' attitudes which would reveal what their "working situation" means to them. A large number of workers were interviewed as regards their viewpoint on work, supervision, and working conditions. Initially, questions considered important by managers and researchers were asked using a direct approach. It was observed that the workers' replies were cautious. Therefore, this approach was replaced by less formal means, where the interviewer only listened to what the workers had to say. The findings confirmed the importance of social factors at work in the total work environment.
4. **Bank Wiring Test Room Experiment:** This was conducted with intentions to arrive at a new system of observing and getting more precise information about social groups within a company and also to find out factors that restrict output. A group of 14 workers was placed under conditions that were mostly normal and observed for some time. After the experiment, when the group's outputs were compared with their earlier outputs, it was noticed that the group developed its own production norms for each individual worker, which was lower than the targets set by the management. Workers would because of this produce only within the group norm, thus defeating the incentive system. Workers who attempted to produce more than the group norms were seen as rate-busters and were isolated, harassed, or punished by the group. The findings of the study are:

- Individual workers were limiting output
- The group had its own “off the record” standards of performance
- Output stood constant over a period of time
- Informal groups play a key part in the functioning of an organization

Effect of Monotony on Productivity

Other experiments were carried out to investigate the effect of fatigue and tedious repetition on productivity and how to manage the situation using variables like breaks from work, work hours, and incentives.

Under normal circumstances, the work hours per week were 48 hours which included Saturdays and no breaks from work. Workers were put on piece-work salaries where they were paid on each part they produced at the first phase of the experiment, the outcome of which was an increase in output. In the second phase, the workers were given 2 breaks from work of 5 minutes each for 5 weeks and again output went up. The third phase saw the breaks from work further increased to 10 minutes and the output skyrocketed. For the fourth phase, 5-6 minutes breaks were given and output dropped a bit, the workers attributed the drop to a break in work pattern. The same conditions used in the third phase were used for the fifth phase with an additional free hot meal given by the company and output rose again. At the sixth phase, workers were allowed to close for the day at 4:30 p.m instead of 5:00 p.m, and an increase in output was recorded.

The seventh phase had the same outcomes as the sixth phase even though the workers were allowed to close for the day by 4.00 p.m. In the eighth and final phase, all upgrades were withdrawn and workers returned to original working conditions. Stunningly, the outcomes concluded that output was the highest ever recorded.

2.2 Findings of the Hawthorne studies

Findings of the experiments revealed that the belief of workers that they are valued, taken care of, and getting opportunities to be involved in decision making contributed more to the rise in productivity and improvement of workers' physical work environment. The key findings of the experiment are:

- Organizations are social systems and are beyond just a techno-economic system: The social systems determine individual roles and establish norms that may vary between organizations
- Employees can be motivated by psychological and social wants because human behavior is influenced by feelings, emotions, and attitudes. Making economic or monetary rewards only one of the motivators but not the sole method of motivation
- Participative management and two-way communication channels are essential instruments because it carries information downward for the proper functioning of an organization and transmits upwards feelings and sentiments of workers in the organization
- Group psychology plays an important role: workers act and react more as group members than as individuals in organizations with groups determining norms of behavior. Informal leaders also emerge as against formal leadership to enforce group norms and help workers function as a social group. The formal leader is rendered useless if he does not conform to group norms
- Emphasis on man as a living machine, and far more important and complex in dealing with than inanimate machines. Hence, it is important to drive employee morale to attain optimum output

2.3 Ground-breaking effect of the Hawthorne studies in the field of Management

The Hawthorne study has been one of the most frequently debated phenomenon in modern work of management. It represents a progression from Taylor's pure scientific management.

The study revealed the importance of psychosocial factors in enhancing workers' productivity and satisfaction.

However, as much as the Hawthorne studies is regarded as a major contributor to organizational management, it had a few flaws which it was criticized upon. Some of the flaws the work was criticized upon are:

- Increase in production could have been as a result of the employees knowing they were being observed
- Human aspect given too much emphasis whereas it cannot improve production alone without other factors
- Important helpful role of supervisors may be lost with excess informality within groups

Works of others authors such as Douglas McGregor and Abraham Maslow on the values of human relations have since been developed building on Mayo's Hawthorne studies.

The Hawthorne studies revealed that employees always desire to be heard and valued, and this is what motivates them and ultimately enhances productivity. The studies showed that while monetary incentive and good working conditions are important, social issues and job satisfaction are even more important in bringing about improvements in people's work performances. The study by incorporating the socio-psychological aspects of humans served as a sociological landmark in the study of industrial enterprise and organization management. It marked the beginning of the factory as a social system, and 'workers' as social rather than inanimate machine man. The studies laid a foundation for what is called Human Resources management today.

3.0 Conclusion

Despite that the Hawthorne effect has been interpreted in many ways and even generated some criticisms, it continues to remain significant in generating new ideas on dynamics of work groups and leadership, job design, motivation and communication. The work led to the emergence of human resources management in modern management and laid foundation for what is referred as employee engagement today. It is a known fact that engaged employees are the most productive ones.

Some ways in which the Hawthorne studies is now being used in modern workplaces are:

- Good listening to: A lot of start-up companies with younger employers are benefitting from this. Employee ideas are being heard, embraced and appreciated. This motivates by giving to a feeling of being involved.
- Observation over vigilance: Despite that employees hate being under vigilance, they still want to be observed. They want superiors to take notice of their good works and be appreciated for the same, without being watched all the time or micromanaged
- Right people in right groups: Productive employees can become unproductive if placed in the wrong group. Attentive and communicative mindfulness of how others are working can however drive their engagement and increase productivity
- Gender diversity: Rate at which women are entering male-dominated professions is on the rise. However, they are often made to feel unwanted by male colleagues, leading to poor productivity. Employers will do well to be more observant and bring in changes to make the environment more conducive.

Finally, organizations are realizing that motivation tools don't necessarily have to be monetary. Sometimes, the little things work wonders in improving productivity.

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